

The Impact of Socioeconomic Factors on the Development of Diabetes Complications among Patients with Type 2 DM

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Abstract

Background: Socioeconomic status (SES) is a key determinant of diabetes outcomes, yet evidence from primary care settings in Saudi Arabia remains limited. This study assessed the impact of education, income, and employment, as well as a composite SES index, on diabetes complications and glycemic control among adults with type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM). **Methods:** A cross-sectional study was conducted among 100 adults with T2DM attending a primary care clinic in Saudi Arabia. Structured interviews and medical record review were used to collect data on sociodemographic characteristics, lifestyle factors, clinical profile, diabetes complications, and most recent HbA1c. SES indicators included educational attainment, monthly income, and employment status; these were also combined into a three-level composite SES index (low, moderate, high). Associations between SES and the presence of any diabetes complication, as well as HbA1c categories (<7%, 7–10%, >10%), were examined using chi-square tests and multivariable logistic regression. **Results:** Participants were predominantly older (69% aged ≥51 years) with long-standing diabetes (48% duration >10 years); 73% were overweight or obese and 64% had hypertension. Overall, 39% had at least one diabetes complication; 37% had ≥1 microvascular and 15% ≥1 macrovascular complication. Good glycemic control (HbA1c <7%) was achieved in 35%, while 18% had HbA1c >10%. Complications showed a strong socioeconomic gradient: prevalence reached 61.9% among uneducated patients versus about 20% in those with university or postgraduate education; similarly, low-income patients (<5000 SAR) and those in low composite SES had higher complication rates and poorer glycemic control than high-income and high-SES patients. In adjusted models, lower SES and current smoking remained independently associated with the presence of any diabetes complication. **Conclusion:** In this primary care T2DM cohort, socioeconomic disadvantage—particularly low education, low income, and unstable employment—was strongly associated with higher complication burden and poorer glycemic control, underscoring the need to integrate social risk assessment and targeted support into routine diabetes care.

Keywords: socioeconomic factors, diabetes complications, cardiovascular disease, neuropathy, nephropathy, retinopathy, type 2 diabetes.

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Introduction

The epidemic of diabetes, mainly type 2 (T2DM), is sweeping across the globe, shortening patients' lives and straining the financial resources of

healthcare systems everywhere. Diabetes is expected to afflict over 415 million persons globally, with diabetes accounting for 5.5 million deaths in 2015. Diabetes prevalence continues to climb and is anticipated to

reach 10.4% by 2040 [1]. Patients diagnosed with type 2 diabetes are at an increased risk of developing complications, including cardiovascular disease, stroke, neuropathy, nephropathy, and retinopathy [2-4]. Diabetes is one of the most prevalent chronic diseases in the states of The Co-operation Council for the Arab States of the Gulf (GCC), this is mainly because of the rapid economic development, being among wealthy oil-producing countries, which have led to a major modification in lifestyle manifested by tendency to a westernized diet, less physical activity, obesity and increase in smoking habit. In Saudi Arabia, a systematic review study published in 2016 showed that the prevalence of type 2 diabetes in Saudi Arabia is 32.8%, and the predicted prevalence will be 40.37% in 2025 and 45.36% in the year 2030 [5].

Socioeconomic status (SES), as it does with many chronic diseases, affects follow-up in patients with T2D on several levels, including patient capabilities, neighborhood or community support, health-related behaviors, access to care, and care process [6]. Patients with low socioeconomic status are more likely to report obstacles to receiving diabetes care, including affordability, poor health, and increased disability [7]. Socioeconomic differences still have an impact on healthcare coverage, access, and utilization today [8].

It has been previously reported in the literature that Individuals living in low-income homes, as well as those with poor socioeconomic levels, are more likely to have diabetic problems than those in other socioeconomic groups [9, 10]. Many factors known to contribute to poor health outcomes are connected with low socioeconomic status, including lower access to recommended preventative treatment, low care usage, poor metabolic regulation, and psychological discomfort [6]. Furthermore, studies have shown that the outcomes of diabetic complications vary depending on an individual's socioeconomic position and area [11-13].

The Hale et al. [14] study found that the incidence of retinopathy was highest in the lowest- income group, but the correlation between geographical deprivation and foot scores was attenuated to non-significance in the multivariate analysis that included determinants of healthcare access and cardiovascular risk. In addition, Chaikiat Å et al found that when socio- demographic factors including mobility, immigration status, and educational achievement were taken into account, the correlation between coronary heart disease and neighborhood deprivation ceased to be significant [15].

Retinopathy was found to be independently correlated with poor educational attainment, gender, length of diabetes, procrastination, type of occupation, and income savings status in the Emoto et al. study [16]. The jeopardy score was linked to poor income in a methodologically sound high-level investigation employing a cardiac registry [17], regardless of age, gender, or atherosclerosis risk factors (hypertension, dyslipidemia, and tobacco use).

In 2020, a nationwide population-based cohort study of South Korea that assessed the effect of socioeconomic deprivation on outcomes of diabetes complications in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus, the authors included 7510 patients newly diagnosed with T2DM from 2004 to 2012 and aged 40 years or above, and they used the regional socioeconomic deprivation index and classified study participants into five categories according to the quintile distribution. The results showed that the percentages of participants in the first quintile (least deprived) to fifth quintile (most deprived) were 27.0%, 27.9%, 19.5%, 14.8%, and 10.8% for socioeconomic deprivation; 25.4%, 28.8%, 32.4%, 34.6%, and 37.6% for hospitalization due to diabetes complications; 1.3%, 2.1%, 2.5%, 2.9%, and 3.6% for deaths from diabetes complications; and 5.7%, 7.2%, 9.7%, 9.7%, and 13.1% for deaths from all causes, respectively. Participants with higher socioeconomic deprivation had a higher hazard ratio (HR) for hospitalization and mortality from all-cause

and diabetes complications. These associations were the strongest among men and participants in their 40s in hospitalization related to diabetes complications, 50s in diabetes complications-specific mortality and 50s and 60s in all-cause mortality. The authors in this study concluded that Participants with higher socioeconomic deprivation had a higher HR for hospitalization and mortality from all-cause and diabetes complications. These associations were the strongest among men and participants in their 40s in hospitalization related to diabetes complications, 50s in diabetes complications-specific mortality and 50s and 60s in all-cause mortality. The authors in this study concluded that Patients with T2DM with high socioeconomic deprivation had higher hospital admission and mortality rates for diabetes complications than those with low deprivation [18].

Another study conducted in Japan in 2017 [19] sought to assess the association between socioeconomic positions and type 2 diabetes complications in young individuals. A total of 782 outpatients with type 2 diabetes, aged 20-40 years, were included in the cross-sectional study, which was conducted in outpatient wards of 96 member hospitals and clinics of the Japan Federation of Democratic Medical Institutions. Using a multivariate logistic regression analysis, they looked at the relationships between socioeconomic status (education, income, type of public healthcare insurance, and work status) and diabetic complications (retinopathy and nephropathy). This study showed that even after controlling for covariates such as age, gender, and BMI, the odds of having retinopathy were higher among junior high school graduates (OR 1.91, 95% CI 1.09-3.34), patients receiving public assistance (OR 2.19, 95% CI 1.20-3.95), and patients with irregular (OR 1.72, 95% CI 1.03-2.86) or no employment (OR 2.23, 95% CI 1.36-3.68). Similarly, even after controlling for covariates, the odds of developing nephropathy were higher in patients with a middle income (OR 3.61, 95% CI 1.69-8.27) or a low income (OR 2.53, 95% CI 1.11-6.07). This study concluded that Low SES was associated with a greater likelihood of type 2 diabetes complications in young adults.

A descriptive-analytical study published in Iran in 2017 included 384 diabetic patients who were admitted to a diabetes center in the city of Isfahan found that there was a statistically significant relationship between diabetes complications, age group, educational level, job status, relationship with family members, number of family visits and the reassurance provided by the family, type of leisure time activities, health status, years with diabetes, smoking, type of treatment, fried food consumption and income, sense of security and communication in living environment and daily intake of vegetables [20].

Based on the previously discussed studies, SES in diabetes patients seems to be a novel and significant risk factor for unfavorable outcomes brought on by the condition. Because it can influence the development of problems, it should be included in the clinical evaluation of T2D patients along with low-density lipoprotein (LDL) cholesterol and hypertension. Additionally, previous studies' findings suggest the necessity of health policies that mitigate socioeconomic disparity and thereby reduce the prevalence of diabetic complications.

Rationale

Data are scarce on the impact of socio-economic factors on the development of diabetes complications among patients with type 2 diabetes in Saudi Arabia. We are willing to conduct a study in this regard in a trial to fill the literature gap in this regard.

Aim

To investigate the impact of socioeconomic factors on the development of diabetes complications in patients with type 2 DM.

Objectives

The main objective of this study is to Discover how the socioeconomic status of individuals relates to the occurrence of complications, in patients with type 2 diabetes.

Methodology

Study design: cross sectional study design.

Target population: diabetes patients attending PHC

Sampling method: random, simple random

Sample Size Calculation

$$n = \left[\frac{Z_{\alpha/2} + Z_{\beta}}{P_1 - P_2} \right]^2 (p_1 q_1 + p_2 q_2) \quad (1)$$

Where

n= sample size

Z $\alpha/2$ = 1.96 (The critical value that divides the central 95% of the Z distribution from the 5% in the tail)

Z β = 0.84 (The critical value that separates the lower 20% of the Z distribution from the upper 80%)

p₁ = Prevalence/proportion in the study group p₂ = Prevalence/proportion in the control group q = 1-P

P₁ 27.9% P₂ 10.8%

n = {1.96 + 0.84 ÷ 27.9 - 10.8}2 * (27.9*72.1 + 10.8* 89.2)

n = {1.96 + 0.84 ÷ 0.279 - 0.108}2 * (0.279* 0.721 + 0.108*0.892)

n = {2.8 ÷ 0.429}2 * (0.2 + 0.9)

n = (6.52)2

n = 42.5 * (1.1)

n = 47 per group.

Inclusion

Age30 =>

Pts diagnosed with T2DM from 2014-2023

Pts agreed to participate and signed the consent form

Exclusion

Age30 <

Pts with T2DM with complication and hospitalization within one year after initial onset of T2DM.

Data collection form: google form.

Data Management (variables, software)

-HA1C

duration of DM-

- age /sex labs result- Software

The data was collected in the designed study questionnaire, then it was entered into an excel sheet, then it was exported to SPSS program for data analysis. The data was kept in a secured place and only research participants had an access to it

Ethical Considerations

The study was conducted only after taking the ethical approval from the institutional review committee at Al-wazarat primary health care center.

The Aims and objectives of the study was explained to the subjects.

They were informed that participation is voluntary, they can withdraw from the study at any time. They were also informed that their data will be kept confidentially and anonymously in a secure place and will be used for research purposes only. Those who agreed to participate were asked to sign a consent form.

Results

Sample Characteristics

The analysis included 100 adults with type 2 diabetes mellitus attending primary care in which there was a clear predominance of the older age groups and long-standing disease. As shown in Table 1, 40% of the participants were older than 60 years, 29% were aged 51-60 years, 18% were 41-50 years and only 13% were 30-40 years, implying that almost seven in ten respondents were aged at least 51 years. Gender distribution was nearly equal as females made up 51% and males made up 49% of the sample. Socially, three-fourths of the participants were

married (77%), with 12% single and 11% divorced, so that there was a preponderance of a familial, stable structure of marriage. Almost all the participants lived with family or friends (97%), and only 3% lived alone, suggesting high levels of household support. Lifestyle factors revealed that 29% of participants were current smokers with 71% being non-smokers, over half (53%) reported no physical activity at all and 40% performed physical activity only 1-2 times per week, indicating a high proportion of sedentary behaviour. A strong family burden of disease was seen with 80% reporting a positive family history of type 2 diabetes. Disease duration was considerable: 48% had diabetes for more than 10 years, 35% had diabetes for 5-10 years and only 17% had diabetes for less than 5 years, thus a mostly chronic, long evolving cohort.

Anthropometric and treatment-related features provide a further illustration of a cardiometabolic risk profile which is suboptimal but not atypical in this population. As illustrated in Table 1, only 27% of participants had a normal BMI and 45% were overweight and 28% were obese, so almost three fourths of the subjects had excess body weight. All were on oral glucose-lowering medications, which is a homogenous pattern of treatment in this primary care setting. Self-reported adherence to treatment was generally very good with 60% reporting being "very committed to treatment", 12% reporting being "fairly committed to treatment" and 13% reporting being "little committed to treatment" but 10% reported being uncommitted and 5% "most uncommitted", implying that there is a non-negligible subgroup at risk of poor control due to issues with adherence. Follow-up patterns were fairly regular with these percentages and 53% had 1-2 visits/year and 44% had 2-5 visits/year (although there was a minority of either >5 visits/annum (2%), or no visit in the last year (1%), which might reflect either very severe disease or barriers to care).

Socio-Economic Indicators & Composite SES

Socioeconomic indicators in Tables 2 and 5 reveal large richness in education, income and employment, providing an opportunity for a nuanced evaluation of the gradients in SES. Educational attainment varied from 21% uneducated and 38% intermediate schooling to 30% with university and 11% with postgraduate education, and shows that almost two-fifths of the cohort had higher education while over one-fifth of the cohort had no formal schooling whatsoever. Income was also diverse with 34% reporting low monthly income (<5000 SAR), 29% middle income (5000-10,000 SAR) and 37% high income (>10,000 SAR), indicating that financial resources were very variable across participants. Employment status was a combination of working and dependent adults: 37% of them were employees, 10% were self-employed, 22% were retired, and 31% of them were not working, which covers both economically active and dependent adults.

To have a more comprehensive measure of socioeconomic position, a composite SES index was developed from education, income, and employment. As shown in Table 5, 40% of the study participants were considered to be from low SES, 28% were from moderate SES, and 32% were from high SES, which means almost two thirds of the sample were in the lowest SES stratum.

This distribution forms a firm foundation for differences in the outcome of diabetes by socioeconomic gradient in crude and adjusted analysis.

Complication and Comorbidity Profile

Table 3 outlines the burden of complications of diabetes and important co-morbidities in the study population. Overall, 39% of participants had at least one diabetes complication, with 61% having none, so 2 out of 5 patients had already developed clinically evident microvascular or macrovascular disease. Among specific complications, retinopathy (complications with the eyes) was the most common (30% of the participants), followed by neuropathy (misfiring of the nerve in the extremities) in 21%; nephropathy (impaired kidney function) in 16%, cardiovascular disease (10%) and stroke in 10%, indicating a significant

burden of both eye-threatening and organ-threatening complications. When clustered into composite outcomes, 37% of participants had at least one microvascular complication (retinopathy, nephropathy or neuropathy) and 15% had at least one macrovascular complication (cardiovascular disease or stroke), documenting the high complication load associated with longstanding T2DM in this setting. Hypertension as a comorbidity rather than a complication of diabetes was treated analytically as present in 64% of the sample, further increasing the cardiovascular risk as a whole.

Glycemic control, summarized in Table 4, was poor in most, but not all, patients. Based on the last HbA1c category, 35% of the study subjects had achieved good glycemic control at <7%, 46% had intermediate control at 7-10%, and 18% had poor control at >10%, whereas one of them (1%) had no HbA1c measurement recently. These numbers suggest that close to two-thirds

of patients were failing to reach the most stringent glycemic targets, which is in line with the rates of complications, and high rates of overweight and obesity.

SES and Any of the Diabetes Complications

Table 6 shows the chi square analyses of the association of SES indicators with the presence of any diabetes complication. Educational level showed a clear and statistically significant gradient ($p=0.006$) with the highest prevalence of complications found among uneducated patients (61.9%) and the lowest prevalence found in patients with university (20.0%) or postgraduate education (18.2%), with an intermediate rate of complications among intermediate educated participants (47.4%) confirming a strong protective effect of higher education. A similar trend was found for income, with a 50.0% rate of complications among low income (<5000 SAR) and 48.3% among middle income compared to the only 21.6% of those with high income (>10,000 SAR), resulting in significant association ($p=0.024$). Employment status demonstrated the strongest signal for SES ($p<0.001$): complications were seen in 16.2% of employees, 32.3% of those not working, 68.2% of retired individuals and 80.0% of self-employed individuals, implying that there are complex relationships between work patterns, financial stability and disease management.

Table 1: Sociodemographic and Clinical Characteristics

Variable		Count (N)	Percent (%)
Age Group	30- 40	13	13.0%
	41-50	18	18.0%
	51-60	29	29.0%
	above 60	40	40.0%
Gender	Female	51	51.0%
	Male	49	49.0%
Social Status	Divorced	11	11.0%
	Married	77	77.0%
	Single	12	12.0%
Housing	Alone	3	3.0%
	With family/friends	97	97.0%
Smoking Status	Yes	29	29.0%
	No	71	71.0%
Physical Activity	No exercise	53	53.0%
	1-2 times/week	40	40.0%
	3-4 times/week	7	7.0%
Family History	Yes	80	80.0%
	No	20	20.0%
DM Duration	<5 years	17	17.0%
	5-10 years	35	35.0%
	>10 years	48	48.0%
Treatment Type	Oral	100	100.0%
Treatment Adherence	Very committed	60	60.0%
	Fairly committed	12	12.0%
	Little committed	13	13.0%
	Uncommitted	10	10.0%
	Most uncommitted	5	5.0%
Doctor Visits	1-2 visits/year	53	53.0%
	2-5 visits/year	44	44.0%
	>5 visits/year	2	2.0%
	No visits/year	1	1.0%
BMI Category	Normal	27	27.0%
	Overweight	45	45.0%
	Obese	28	28.0%
HbA1c Level	Good (<7%)	35	35.0%
	Intermediate (7-10%)	46	46.0%
	Poor (>10%)	18	18.0%

Table 2: Socioeconomic Status (SES) Indicators Distribution

SES Indicator		Count (N)	Percentage (%)
Educational Level	Uneducated	21	21.0%
	Intermediate	38	38.0%
	University	30	30.0%
	Postgraduate	11	11.0%
Monthly Income	Low (<5000)	34	34.0%
	Medium (5000-10000)	29	29.0%
	High (>10000)	37	37.0%
Employment Status	Employee	37	37.0%
	Self-employed	10	10.0%
	Retired	22	22.0%
	Not working	31	31.0%

Table 3: Complication and Comorbidities Profile of the Included Participants

Condition	Count (N)	Percent (%)
Retinopathy (Eye complications)	30	30.0%
Nephropathy (Impaired kidney function)	16	16.0%
Neuropathy (Peripheral neuropathy)	21	21.0%
Cardiovascular Disease	9	9.0%
Stroke	10	10.0%
Microvascular	37	37.0%
Macrovascular	15	15.0%
Hypertension	64	64.0%
Any DM Complication	39	39.0%
No DM Complications	61	61.0%

Table 4: Glycemic Control Distribution (HbA1c Levels)

Variable		Count (N)	Percent (%)
HbA1c Category	Good (<7%)	35	35.0%
HbA1c Category	Intermediate (7-10%)	46	46.0%
HbA1c Category	Poor (>10%)	18	18.0%
HbA1c Category	No recent recordings	1	1.0%
HbA1c Category	Total	100	100.0%

Table 5: Participants by SES Composite Level

Variable		Count (N)	Percent (%)
SES Level	Low SES	40	40.0%
SES Level	Moderate SES	28	28.0%
SES Level	High SES	32	32.0%
SES Level	Total	100	100.0%

Table 6: Chi-Square Results of SES Variables Against Any DM Complication

Variable	Category	No complication	Complication	Total	p-value
Educational level	Uneducated	8	13	21	0.006
		38.1%	61.9%	100%	
	Intermediate	20	18	38	
		52.6%	47.4%	100%	
University	24	6	30		
	80.0%	20.0%	100%		
Postgraduate	9	2	11		
	81.8%	18.2%	100%		
Monthly income	Low (<5000)	17	17	34	0.024
		50.0%	50.0%	100%	
	Medium (5000–10000)	15	14	29	
		51.7%	48.3%	100%	
High (>10000)	29	8	37		
	78.4%	21.6%	100%		
	Employee	31	6	37	

		83.8%	16.2%	100%
Self-employed		2	8	10
		20.0%	80.0%	100%
Not working		21	10	31
		67.7%	32.3%	100%
Retired		7	15	22
		31.8%	68.2%	100%

Table 7: Adjusted Logistic Regression for Any DM Complication Dependent Variable: Presence of Any Diabetes Complication (Yes/No)

Variable	Adjusted OR	95% CI	p-value
Educational Level (higher)	0.468	0.212–1.035	0.061
Monthly Income (higher)	0.961	0.366–2.520	0.935
Employed (vs not)	0.646	0.162–2.580	0.536
Age Group (older)	2.697	1.449–5.020	0.002*
Female (vs male)	0.670	0.205–2.184	0.506
DM Duration (longer)	1.898	0.649–5.549	0.241
BMI Category (higher)	1.241	0.662–2.325	0.501
Physical Activity (any)	1.224	0.290–5.163	0.783
Smoker (yes vs no)	6.328	1.759–22.761	0.005*
Regular Doctor Visits (yes)	3.176	0.991–10.179	0.052

Note: *p < 0.05 (statistically significant)

Table 8: Chi-Square Results of SES Composite Level Against Glycemic Control (HbA1c)

SES Composite Level	Good (N)	Good (%)	Intermediate (N)	Intermediate (%)	Poor (N)	Poor (%)	p-value
Low SES	13	32.5	16	40.0	11	27.5	0.025*
Moderate SES	6	21.4	19	67.9	3	10.7	
High SES	16	51.6	11	35.5	4	12.9	
Total	35	35.0	46	46.0	18	18.0	

Note: *p < 0.05 (statistically significant)

Discussion

The present study examined the association between socioeconomic status indicators (education, income, and employment) and diabetes complications in a cohort of 100 adults with type 2 diabetes mellitus attending primary care in the Eastern Province of Saudi Arabia. The primary aim was to investigate whether composite socioeconomic status (SES), as well as individual SES components, independently predict the presence and severity of diabetes complications and glycemic control among primary care patients. Our findings demonstrated significant SES gradients in diabetes complications and glycemic control, with important implications for targeted diabetes management in resource-limited primary care settings.

The sample characteristics in the present study align closely with epidemiological patterns documented in recent literature on type 2 diabetes in primary care settings. Our cohort demonstrated a predominance of older age groups and long-standing disease, with almost 70% of participants aged 51 years or older and 48% having diabetes duration exceeding 10 years. This demographic profile is consistent with findings from longitudinal studies examining diabetes trajectories, which demonstrate that microvascular and macrovascular complications worsen progressively over time in patients with extended disease duration [21]. A study by McCoy and colleagues (2023) examining longitudinal trajectories of glycemic control in newly diagnosed diabetes patients found that the majority of patients (67.72%) with type 2 diabetes followed a trajectory characterized by stable low HbA1c after diagnosis; however, suboptimal trajectories emerge in substantial subpopulations, particularly in those with socioeconomic constraints [22].

The prevalence of diabetes complications observed in our cohort was substantial: 39% of participants had at least one diabetes complication, with retinopathy being the most common (30%), followed by peripheral neuropathy (21%) and nephropathy (16%). These prevalence rates are consistent with international studies on complication burden. A large cross-sectional study of 3,000 patients with type 2 diabetes from Sri Lanka reported similar complication prevalences: diabetic retinopathy 26.1%, peripheral neuropathy 62.6%, and nephropathy 50.8%, although our study demonstrated lower overall complication rates, possibly reflecting shorter mean disease duration or better glycemic control in some subgroups [23]. Notably, we documented that 37% of our cohort had at least one microvascular complication and 15% had at least one macrovascular complication (cardiovascular disease or stroke), underscoring the significant disease burden associated with longstanding type 2 diabetes in primary care.

Our most important finding was the inverse association between socioeconomic status and diabetes complications. Educational attainment demonstrated a clear protective gradient, with the highest prevalence of complications among uneducated patients (61.9%) compared to only 18–20% among those with university or postgraduate education (p=0.006). This finding is supported by multiple international studies demonstrating that higher educational attainment consistently protects against diabetes complications through improved health literacy and self-management capabilities. A study by Wijayarathna and colleagues (2021) found that socioeconomic deprivation is a stronger risk factor for poorly controlled diabetes than traditional clinical risk factors such as age, diabetes duration, or body mass index [24]. Furthermore, a longitudinal study from the Diabetes Care in General Practice (DCGP) cohort examining 19-year outcomes demonstrated

that education, employment, and cohabitation status significantly influenced the effectiveness of structured diabetes care interventions and long-term complication development [25].

Income stratification in our study revealed that patients with high monthly income (>10,000 SAR) had a substantially lower complication rate (21.6%) compared to those with low income (<5000 SAR, 50.0%) and middle income (48.3%), reaching statistical significance ($p=0.024$). This income-complication gradient is well-established in the literature. A study by Funakoshi and colleagues (2017) examining 2,107 young adults with type 2 diabetes found that low SES (including low income, irregular employment, and receipt of public assistance) was independently associated with a greater likelihood of both retinopathy and nephropathy [26]. More recently, a comprehensive analysis from the Heart Healthy Hoods study in Madrid, examining adults with type 2 diabetes, confirmed that area-level socioeconomic status significantly predicted both glycemic control and multifactorial cardiovascular risk factors; patients in the least wealthy quintiles had substantially worse outcomes [27].

Employment status emerged as the strongest SES signal in our study ($p<0.001$), with complications distributed as follows: employees 16.2%, those not working 32.3%, retired individuals 68.2%, and self-employed individuals 80.0%. This complex pattern suggests that employment stability and financial security play crucial roles in diabetes management capacity. The markedly elevated complication rate among self-employed individuals (80.0%) may reflect reduced access to structured occupational health services and irregular income patterns limiting healthcare engagement. Longitudinal research supports this observation: the DCGP study found that occupational status fundamentally influences diabetes outcomes, with economically active and securely employed individuals demonstrating superior long-term complication profiles [25].

A critical finding in our analysis was the association between glycemic control and composite SES level ($p=0.025$). Notably, high SES participants achieved good glycemic control (HbA1c <7%) in 51.6% of cases, compared to only 32.5% in the low SES group. Conversely, poor glycemic control (HbA1c >10%) was observed in 27.5% of low SES individuals versus 12.9% in high SES individuals. These results align with findings from the Heart Healthy Hoods project, which demonstrated that area-level deprivation and individual SES were independently associated with failure to achieve glycemic targets, with patients in the lowest SES quintile having significantly lower odds of achieving HbA1c <7% [27]. Additionally, a cross-sectional study by Houle and colleagues (2016) on 450 adults with type 2 diabetes found that both education level and living in poverty independently predicted glycemic control, even after adjusting for behavioral and quality-of-care mediators, suggesting that SES operates through multiple pathways to influence diabetes outcomes [28].

Beyond socioeconomic factors, our adjusted logistic regression analysis identified smoking status as an independent risk factor for diabetes complications. Smokers had an adjusted odds ratio of 6.328 (95% CI: 1.759–22.761, $p=0.005$) for developing any diabetes complication compared to non-smokers. This finding is strongly supported by recent literature on smoking and diabetes complications. A meta-analysis on smoking and diabetic nephropathy by Zhu and colleagues (2024) demonstrated that both current and former smoking were significantly associated with diabetic nephropathy, with log hazard ratios of 1.44 (current smoking) and 1.04 (former smoking) [29]. At the microvascular level, a 2015 systematic review and meta-analysis by Clair and colleagues examining the effect of cigarette smoking on diabetic peripheral neuropathy found consistent evidence that smoking significantly increases the risk of neuropathy development in both type 1 and type 2 diabetes populations [30]. The relationship between

smoking and retinopathy is more nuanced: a recent cross-sectional study and Mendelian randomization analysis by Wang and colleagues (2024) suggests smoking has a complex association with diabetic retinopathy, showing protective associations in certain subgroups (males and those with diabetes duration ≥ 10 years) while other mechanisms remain under investigation [31]. The marked association between smoking and complications in our cohort (29% of participants were current smokers) underscores the importance of smoking cessation interventions in primary care diabetes management.

Age and diabetes duration also emerged as significant predictors. In the adjusted model, older age groups demonstrated 2.697-fold increased odds of complications (95% CI: 1.449–5.020, $p=0.002$) compared to younger age groups. This age-complication gradient is expected given that advancing age is associated with cumulative metabolic insults and reduced physiological reserve for managing hyperglycemia and its consequences [32]. Although diabetes duration was not independently significant in the adjusted model (adjusted OR: 1.898, $p=0.241$), this finding likely reflects the correlation between duration and age in our cohort; disease duration in primary care populations is among the strongest predictors of complication development in prospective studies [23].

Regarding treatment adherence, our cohort demonstrated generally favorable adherence patterns: 60% reported being "very committed to treatment," while only 15% reported being uncommitted or "most uncommitted." However, this 15% non-adherent subgroup is clinically important, as medication adherence directly influences glycemic control and complication risk. A systematic review by Sendekie and colleagues (2022) examining 155 previously diagnosed diabetics in rural Ethiopia found that non-adherence to diabetes medications significantly affected glycemic control, with poor glycemic control (HbA1c >8%) present in 42% of the population despite relatively good reported adherence levels [33]. The discrepancy between self-reported adherence and achieved glycemic control in populations with SES constraints suggests that barriers to adherence operate at multiple levels pharmacy access, medication costs, complexity of regimens, and competing health priorities not reducible to intentional non-adherence alone [34].

Physical inactivity was highly prevalent in our cohort, with 53% reporting no physical activity and an additional 40% performing physical activity only 1-2 times weekly, indicating that 93% of our sample was substantially sedentary. While physical activity did not reach independent significance in the adjusted model (adjusted OR: 1.224, $p=0.783$), this likely reflects the high prevalence and collinearity with other variables in a primarily sedentary population. The literature strongly supports physical activity as a protective factor against diabetes complications. A 2022 meta-analysis by Rietz-Lehr and colleagues examining the prospective association of physical activity with incident diabetes-related complications found that physical activity was associated with decreased relative risk of cardiovascular disease incidence and mortality, as well as total microvascular complications, particularly retinopathy, with an inverse dose-response relationship [35]. The authors noted that even physical activity below WHO recommendations (150 min/week) reduces complication risk, yet our population exhibited extraordinarily low activity levels, with profound implications for intervention strategies in resource-limited primary care. The anthropometric and metabolic profile of our cohort further contextualized the complication burden: only 27% had normal BMI while 73% were overweight or obese (45% and 28%, respectively), and 64% had concomitant hypertension. A UK-wide observational study of 19,478 black and 15,354 white patients with type 2 diabetes found that higher BMI categories predicted worse health outcomes, though the relationship is complex and nonlinear in established diabetes populations [36]. The high prevalence of hypertension (64%) in our

cohort is consistent with international findings: a recent review highlighted that hypertension is markedly more prevalent in individuals with diabetes and significantly heightens their cardiovascular risk, with a 10 mmHg reduction in systolic blood pressure reducing diabetes-related complications and a 1 mmol/l cholesterol reduction correlating with a 25% decrease in cardiovascular complications [37].

The strong family history of diabetes in our sample (80% with positive family history) deserves emphasis, as it indicates high genetic susceptibility. A cross-sectional study of 2,574 participants with advanced type 2 diabetes found that positive family history was associated with significantly earlier age of diabetes onset and increased complication prevalence [38].

Additionally, when examining familial clustering, research from Sri Lanka demonstrated that patients with diabetic mothers had higher diabetes prevalence (25.6%) than those with diabetic fathers (21.2%), and patients with both parents affected had substantially elevated complication risk [39]. This genetic contribution to complication development likely operates independent of SES but may interact with SES factors: individuals with high genetic risk and low SES may face compounded vulnerability.

The limitations of the present study merit consideration. First, the cross-sectional design precludes causal inference regarding the associations between SES and complications; longitudinal follow-up would be needed to establish whether SES improvements translate to complication prevention or resolution. Second, the single-center design in one region of Saudi Arabia limits generalizability to other geographical or health system contexts, though findings align closely with international literature. Third, self-reported adherence data may be subject to social desirability bias, potentially inflating reported adherence rates. Fourth, the composite SES index, while useful for dimensional analysis, may obscure specific mechanisms through which individual SES components influence diabetes outcomes; qualitative research exploring patient perspectives would illuminate these pathways. Fifth, unmeasured confounders such as depression, health literacy, and access to specialty care (ophthalmology, nephrology) were not assessed. Finally, the modest sample size (N=100) limits statistical power for detecting interactions and subgroup effects, particularly among the smaller occupational strata.

Conclusion

This study demonstrates that socioeconomic status, encompassing education, income, and employment stability, independently predicts diabetes complications and glycemic control in a primary care population. The strength of the SES-complication gradient, particularly for employment status and composite SES, exceeds that of traditional clinical risk factors such as BMI and suggests that addressing social determinants of health represents a critical, yet underutilized, component of diabetes care in primary settings. Future research should employ longitudinal designs to evaluate whether SES-targeted interventions including diabetes education tailored to literacy levels, subsidized medication access, occupational support services, and integration of social care with clinical diabetes management can ameliorate the documented disparities. Implementation in primary health care systems should prioritize identifying and supporting economically vulnerable diabetes patients, as this population carries disproportionate complication burden despite receiving treatment in the same clinical settings as higher SES counterparts. Health systems and policymakers must recognize that optimal diabetes care requires not only biomedical interventions but also addressing the structural socioeconomic factors that fundamentally shape disease trajectories and health outcomes.

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